

Three-dimensional Numerical Analysis of Atherosclerosis Development Within Carotid Artery

Smiljana Djorovic, Igor Saveljic and Nenad Filipovic *Member IEEE*

Abstract— The main purpose of this study was to computationally simulate the plaque progression within carotid artery, by examining the wall shear stress. Mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall was coupled with the blood flow and modelled by the convection–diffusion equations. Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in lumen of the vessel was described using Kedem-Katchalsky equations. Baseline and follow-up time periods were considered. The results of the analysis have shown that the zones of plaque accumulation and progression were correlated with zones of lower shear stress. This was confirmed at the follow-up, where simulation results have shown that carotid lumen was reduced due to plaque progression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Atherosclerosis is caused by building up of plaque and its progression within arteries, due to deposits of fat, cholesterol, calcium, and other substances in the blood. Computational modelling of atherosclerosis has been performed last years, while the mechanisms of atherosclerosis have been used to provide insights for the understanding of the processes which lead to the plaque initiation and progression, as well as to predict plaque regions and mechanisms which are prone to disease progression [1, 2].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The 3D finite element model of the carotid artery was created using the patient-specific CT scan images in combination with several different software packages. The 3D blood flow was governed by the Navier-Stokes equations and continuity equation. Mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall was coupled with the blood flow and modelled by the convection–diffusion equations. Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in lumen of the vessel was described using Kedem-Katchalsky equations. The average blood properties were prescribed and the PAK software [3] was used for the computational simulation, which calculated the wall shear stress. Appropriate boundary conditions were employed, such as: prescribed blood velocity at the inlet of the arterial segment and physiological resistance pressure at the arterial outlets.

*This paper is supported by the TAXINOMISIS project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 755320. This article reflects only the author’s view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The research is also supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (project numbers III41007 and ON174028).

S. Djorovic, I. Saveljic, N. Filipovic are with the Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac, and Bioengineering Research and Development Center - BioIRC, Kragujevac, Serbia (e-mails: smiljana@kg.ac.rs, isaveljic@kg.ac.rs, fica@kg.ac.rs).

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The 3D blood flow was simulated together with the LDL transport through the lumen and artery wall, coupling the plaque progression in vessel wall. The quantification of the real patient-specific plaque progression is investigated. The hemodynamic parameter such as wall shear stress was determined at the baseline and follow-up time periods (Fig. 1). Analyzing the shear stress distribution along the carotid artery at the baseline (Fig. 1. (a)), the yellow circle indicates the zone of a low shear stress value; mean value 0.39 to 0.78 Pa, measured in cross sections at distances 0.5 mm. The marked area represents the greatest risk of plaque position and progression, which is confirmed after the follow-up (Fig. 1. (b)). Development of atherosclerosis leads to increase of plaque volume and decrease of lumen diameter, which is followed by reduced blood flow through stenotic zone and higher shear stress (maximum value: 7.00 Pa). The carotid diameter is approximately 50% reduced comparing with baseline [1, 2].

The estimation of diameter reduction is significant for further steps in medical treatment and prognosis. The results of the analysis have shown that sites with lower shear stress values were correlated with the sites of plaque accumulation and progression. The presented study has shown potential benefit for the prediction of disease progression.

Figure 1. (a) Baseline and (b) follow-up shear stress distribution

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Filipovic, Z. Teng, M. Radovic, et al., “Computer simulation of three dimensional plaque formation and progression in the carotid artery,” *Med Biol Eng Comput*, vol. 51, pp. 607–616, 2013.
- [2] N. Filipovic, I. Saveljic, D. Nikolic, Z. Milosevic, P. Kovacevic and L. Velicki, “Numerical simulation of blood flow and plaque progression in carotid–carotid bypass patient specific case,” *Computer Aided Surgery*, vol. 20(1), pp. 1–6, 2015.
- [3] N. Filipovic, M. Kojic, M. Ivanovic, B. Stojanovic, L. Otasevic, V. Rankovic, “MedCFD, Specialized CFD Software for Simulation of Blood Flow through Arteries,” University of Kragujevac: Kragujevac, Serbia, 2006.